

CORAŚĀSTRA- (THE ART OF THIEVING) IN JAIN LITERATURE

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INTRODUCTION

Indian Society had a rich contribution to literature from the Ancient past that deals a lot about the religion, social, political, philosophical and other aspects in great detail. They based their activities on *Dharma*, *Artha*, *Kāma* and *Mokṣa* thus leading a balanced blissful life in harmony with Nature. At the same time, society was tied down by anti-social behaviours time and again leading to crimes that were punishable. Among the different forms of crime in vogue, theft (*Steya*) was common and had been specially treated much in literature. Stealing or theft is an outcome of man's natural instincts when he is unguarded by morality, ethics and legal code. The harmful activities of thieves and robbers, their characteristics, skills used, the articles stolen and the punishment given by society to them find rich description in ancient texts. Such descriptions of theft in ancient Indian literature especially Sanskrit texts and fiction have been dealt by various scholars like Maurice Bloomfield¹, K.V.Sharma² and K. N. Jadhav³. The present paper briefly gives a description of these contributions with special attention to theft in some ancient Jain literature.

THEFT IN VEDIC AND EPIC TEXTS

A study of Vedic literature reveals that from very early period Indians were disturbed by criminal activities of robbers and thieves. The *R̥gveda*⁴ makes specific mention of thieves (*steya*) RV (I.65.1) and robbers (*Taskara*) in RV (4.38.5). There were instances of theft of cattle as evident in the case of *Pāṇis* who stole the cattle and hid them in caves. *Saramā*, the heavenly bitch had discovered them on the request of Indra. RV (6.29.6) states that *Pūṣan* knew the various paths and treasures as well as thieves. The *Vājasaneyī Saṁhitā*⁵ (YV) [10.79] classifies four kinds of thieves of which *Sāyaṇācārya*, the commentator describes as –

stenā guptacorāḥ taskarā prakāṭacorāḥ atiprakatā nirbhayāḥ grāmeṣu bandikarā malimlavaḥ

Early law givers elaborate many details about theft as it had affected society too much. The *Manusmṛti*⁶ [8.332] mentions two types of theft namely 'Steya' (stolen in a person's absence without his knowledge) and 'Sāhasa' (stolen forcibly from a person in his presence). *Nārada Smṛti*⁷ [XIV.12-13] defines theft as an act done by fraud either openly or in a concealed manner. Theft is again declared by the wise to be of three sorts according to the value of the stolen goods, since articles of inferior, middling and superior value may be stolen. *Bṛhaspati Smṛti*⁸ [XXII.2] holds that thieves are subdivided into 1000 folds according to their skill, ability and method of cheating. He states that cheats, fraudulent traders are open thieves while house breakers, robbers and stealers are secret thieves. *Yājñavalkya Smṛti*⁹ [II.275] states the gravity of theft was decided in accordance with value of stolen article. These texts prescribe nominal fines, death sentences and other types of punishment according to gravity of theft committed. *Bṛhaspati* held the view that for stealing grass, wood, flowers, fruits the criminal should have his hand cut off and stealers of grain should pay fine 10 times the price of stolen amount. *Nārada* prescribes fine of 8 times the amount for stealing articles sold by weight and measure. Likewise for lifting domestic

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animals, the fine was according to its size and value. The text also prescribes punishment for cut purse or openers of knots of cloth (*Granthibhedaka*). Further the text also deals on robbers who infested a country, village or house or those who disturbed sacrificial acts. *Nārada* states that a dog's foot was branded on forehead when a *Brāhmaṇa* committed theft. Harmful activities of thieves and robbers are also mentioned in Sage *Vyāsa's Mahābhārata*¹⁰. The episode of Sage *Māṇḍavya* who was impaled on a stake mistaking him for a thief who dropped his stolen goods at his hut is mentioned by the text. The theft of butter and clothes by Lord *Kṛṣṇa* is well described in various *Purāṇas*.

THEFT IN POST-VEDIC TEXTS

Several Post -Vedic texts offer a rich glimpse of the art of stealing. *Kauṭilya* in his *Arthaśāstra*¹¹ (AS) [III.17] refers to thieves and robbers as pests of society. He distinguishes between robbery and theft. The question as to whether to regard theft as being an act in accordance to *Dharma* or whether it was *Adharma* is still puzzling as later texts show. Poet *Kālidāsa* says theft of precious jewels was punishable by death. In his work, *Mālavikāgnimitram*¹² he refers to highway robbery [V.90].

Founders of the science or art of Theft and their manuals

Sanskrit literature harbors a widespread tradition that there exists a Manual of thievery called '*Choraśāstra*'. A thief's manual of a systematic nature is found in the *Atharvaveda Pariśiṣṭa*¹³ known as *Dhūrtakalpa* or *Skandha Yāga* that has been edited by scholars¹⁴. It precribes the worship of Lord Skandha (also known as *Kārtikeya*). *Mūladeva* (also known as *Karṇīsuta* or *Gaṇikāputra*) is supposed to be an arch thief and supreme preceptor of all thieves. His story is narrated by himself to a king in the '*Kathāsaritasāgara*'¹⁵ of *Somadeva*. Another story of *Mūladeva* is preserved in *Devendra vṛtti*¹⁶ (a commentary) on the Jain text '*Uttarādhyāyanasūtra*'. He is known as *Karṇīsuta*, an author of science of thieving (*steyaśāstrapravartaka*). He is also mentioned in the '*Vetālapañcaviṃśatī*'¹⁷ of *Śivadāsa*, '*Śukasaptatī*'¹⁸ and '*Bṛhatkathāmañjarī*'¹⁹ of *Kṣemendra*. The various stories of *Mūladeva* are dealt by scholars²⁰. The '*Padacandrikā*' commentary by *Kavīndrācārya Sarasvatī* on poet *Daṇḍin's* '*Daśakumāracaritam*'²¹ [*Ucchvāsa* II] mentions *Karṇīsuta* as an author of science of theft –

karṇīsutaprahite karṇīsutaḥ steyaśāstrakartā tena prahite pravartite |

The '*Maṭṭavilāsa Prahasanam*'²² (580-630 A. D.) mentions *Kharapaṭa* as one who promulgated the science of theft. *Satyasoma*, a mendicant asks *Nāgasena* to pay reverence to *Kharapaṭa* as –

namaḥ khaṭapaṭāyēti vaktavyam yena coraśāstram praṇītam |

He further comments that Lord Buddha may be superior to *Kharapaṭa* in this field as he formulated his canons by gathering ideas from *Mahābhārata* and *Vedānta* texts. The *Kauṭilya's* *Arthaśāstra* AS [IV.8.24] also mentions *Kharapaṭa*.

The *Mṛcchakaṭikā*²³ (MC) of *Śūdraka* throws interesting details on art of stealing. *Lalladīkṣitā*, the commentator of *Mṛcchakaṭikā* gives such quotes from ancient works. In this text, the thief

Śārvilaka speaks about himself as being Skandha's son. From his soliloquy as in MC [Act III], it is assumed that works on *Choraśāstra* attributed to Skandha (Lord Kārtikeya), Kanakaśakti, Bhāskaranandin, Devavrata and Yogācārya existed. Daṇḍin's *Daśakumāracaritam* also describes similarly the science of burglary. He states that there was a standard book on 'House Breaking' attributed to 'Kaṛṇīsuta' used by thieves. He was known by the names Gaṇikāputra and identified as Mūladeva.

Tools of a thief, his methods and types of breaches

Daṇḍin's *Daśakumāracaritam*²⁴ states that a thief generally surveyed the house, carried necessary equipments like scissors (*Kākali*), tongs (*Samdamśaka*), magic powder (*Yogacūrṇa*), magic lamp (*Yogavarttikā*), hook (*Karkaṭaka*), rope (*Rajju*), casket containing bees (*Bhramarakaraṇḍaka*) for extinguishing light, or a dummy wooden head or image of a man (*Pratipuruṣa*).

Thieves are also supposed to know many charms by which they can make themselves invisible, turn water into fire, break open locks [*Tālodghāṭinī*] or to make everyone asleep in the house using *Yogachūrṇa* [magic powder] by means of the *Avasvāpini Vidyā*.

The theft was initiated by digging a tunnel or cutting a breach into the house. These breaches (*Khātra*) had special names such as *Bhāskara*, *Bālacandra*, *Vāpī*, *Vistīrṇa*, *Svastika*, *Pūrṇakumbha*, *Padma*, *Akāśa* and so on as stated in MC [Act III, verse 13]. The same text MC [Act III] has Śārvilaka quoting Kanakaśakti who has laid down four types of breach making processes as tabulated in **Tab. 1**.

Tab. 1. Types of houses and breaches made by a thief as in *Mṛcchakaṭikā* (MC) of Śūdraka

Type of house	Mode of Breach
House made of burnt bricks	Remove the bricks to enter
House made of unbaked bricks	Bricks are Flaked
Clay house	Bricks soaked or sprinkled with water
House made of wood	Cut is made to make a breach

Bhāsa's drama *Chārudattam*²⁵ dealing in a section on burglary gives other names of breaches not specified by MC such as those shaped like mouth of a crocodile (*Jhaṣāsyā*), elephant (*Gajāsyā*), tiger (*Vyāghravaktra*), Full Moon (*Pūrṇacandra*), Crescent Moon (*Ardhachandra*) and triangular. The *Buddhist Jātakas*²⁶ flourish interesting details on theft. In the *Mahilāmukha Jātaka* thieves describe the way to dig a tunnel into a house, break the walls. It instructs that a burglar should get rid of all goodness and virtue. The *Sattigumba Jātaka* speaks of a robber village of 500 robbers.

Lakṣmaṇa kavi in his '*Rāmāyaṇachampū*'²⁷ attests that the art of stealing was one among the 64 arts.

*añjanam naradr̥ṣṭestu vañcanam svaravañcanam | mañimantrauśadhīnām ca siddhayaś
corakarma ca ||*

An important thief manual titled ‘*Shaṅmukhakaḷpa*’²⁸ in the *Asiatic Society of Kolkata* has some details of art of stealing. It deals on various charms for collyriums to make one invisible, to break open locks (*Tālodghāṭana*), to put inmates of house to sleep invoking demon Kumbhakarna (of ‘*Rāmāyaṇa*’ fame). There are charms to inspect treasures, for arresting (*stambhana*) of fire and water, rites to make inmates of city asleep [*Nagaraśāntikartukāmaḥi*], various magic pills [*Guṭikāyoga*]. The *Śivatattvaratnākara*²⁹ of Kelaḍi Basavarāja, an Encyclopaedic text defines theft as taking away by any of the several deceptive means the property of persons asleep, disordered in intellect or intoxicated [VIII.1.228]. The text states that thieves may be detected and caught by officers either by tracing their footsteps, seizing one who has been convicted already [VIII.1.229 -230]. There are different rules determining punishment for different types of thefts. A *Brāhmaṇa* should be branded and banished from kingdom [VIII.1.233]. Stealers of horses, elephants and cows are to be impaled on stakes [VIII.1.236] while punishments like cutting of hands, feet or awarding death are prescribed for stealing articles like gold, precious stones and clothes [VIII.1.239-241]. The ‘*Dharmacauryarasāyaṇa*’³⁰ of Gopālayogīndra is brief work in about 275 lines in which the ethics of thievery are highlighted in a tale of a brahmin thief named Dharmasaṅgrahin. It was composed either in Andhra Pradesh or Tamil Nadu perhaps not more than 200 or 300 years ago. It propounds ‘*Steya*’ (or theft) as a Dharma based on the *Śāstra* principles involved in finding the proper place and locations for burglary, the time involved and so on as king Dharmaketu is led by the brahmin into the city pointing out various houses that could be robbed and the latter stating that wealth stolen in these houses had to be earned by righteous means. Only then could a thief could rob them. Finally this leaves the king’s palace itself that can be robbed. Several other aspects of this work have been dealt by scholars³¹. The ‘*Dhūrtākhyāna*’³² of Haribhadrasūrī mentions four rogues (or thieves including Mūladeva) meeting at an old park north of city of Ujjain narrating their experiences.

THEFT IN JAIN LITERATURE

The Jain canonical texts consists of the 12 *Aṅgas*, 12 *Upāṅgas*, *Chedasūtras*, *Mūlasūtras* and *Chūlikasūtras* with their commentaries. Of these, the texts speak on several aspects of the art of stealing that are dealt as below.

The ‘*Uttarādhyāyanasūtra*’³³ (UDS) [9.28] mentions several types of robbers and burglars. It states that robbers were experts in making breaches in the walls of houses like *Kaviśisa* (*Kapiśīrṣā* – Cornice shape), *Kalaśa* (pot), *Nandāvarta* (flower or fish shape), lotus and other human shape. The *Vṛtti* (commentary) of Devendra on the same text UDS mentions the story of robber Maṇḍiya of Beṇṇāyada who worked as a tailor during day time and robbed during the night. He smeared his knees with ointment on the pretext of having some sores and walked with support of a wooden staff. By night, he dug breaches into houses, depositing the stolen goods in an underground cell outside the town. Close to the cave in the outskirts of the city his sister dwelt who pretended to wash the feet of those who carried the loot from underground cell into the cave, pushing them to death inside the well in the cave. One day Mūladeva who had learnt of the citizen’s complaints came to the place. Hiding at night there, Mūladeva tricked Maṇḍiya and bought him to the king who then sought his sister’s hand in marriage for a dowry. The king cleverly procures all the stolen goods on this pretext and then impales Maṇḍiya.

The ‘*Bṛhatkalpabhāṣya*’³⁴ mentions about thieves who destroyed ships, extracted money at the point of sword and entered into residences of monks.

Another Jain text namely ‘*Vipākasūtra*’³⁵ (known as *Vivāgasūya*)’ gives description of torture instruments to thieves in prison like iron jars filled with copper, jars containing urine of animals, fetters, wooden frames to fasten feet, whips, stones, clubs, ropes and so on. It also mentions about a robber settlement (*Chorapalli*) in the dense forests of *Sālāṭavī*, a place north of *Pūrṇimatāla* city. The ‘*Vipākasūtra*’ also elaborates on the details of this hideout and states that it was impregnable, surrounded by bamboo thickets, boulders, gorges and natural waterfalls. It was an unapproachable mountain ravine having caves and secret passages for entry-exits and also having its own water supply. The text further elaborates that bandit leader Vijaya was the undisputed leader of 500 thieves in *Sālāṭavī*. He was proficient in aiming objects by hearing sound [*Saddavehī* or *śabdabhedī*]. The text states that Vijaya taught several magical spells of art of stealing to Cilāya, a slave boy of merchant Dhanna of *Rāyagiha* [*Rājagrha*] who joined his gang. The ‘*Vipākasūtra*’ also has another interesting episode of *Choraśāstra* while narrating the story of thief Abhagnasena and his 500 bandits. He also lived in *Sālāṭavī* hideout. The text mentions several rituals performed by robbers for success of their mission. These include a sumptuous banquet with various food delicacies, some ritual marks applied on the forehead for success, followed by the ritual of ‘*Ardhacarma Ārohaṇa*’ [riding over wet leather] and finally equipping themselves with iron armour and weapons. Ācārya Abhayadevasūri commenting on these rituals states that ‘*Ardhacarma Ārohaṇa*’ was an auspicious ritual to remove all possible hurdles conveying the bond of unwavering resolve.

Another Jain text ‘*Nāyādhammakāhao*’³⁶ narrates some other episodes of the thief Vijaya. It adds that Vijaya kidnapped Devadutta, son of Dhanna and threw him in a well where he died. Dhanna also was in prison for some reason wherein thief Vijaya also was caught and both were together bound by feet in same wooden frame. This incident shows how thieves were punished. After Vijaya died, Cilāya became a ring leader of bandits and attacked city where Dhanna lived. He recited spells to open locks of the gates [*Tāluggahādānī vijja*], took out water from his water bag [*Udaḡabatti*] and sprinkled it over the doors. When they opened, he looted the wealth of citizens and kidnapped Dhanna’s daughter. The text further adds that a thief who had murdered the daughter of Dhanna to steal the ornaments was punished by blows showered on his body, binding him behind with ropes, suspending the stolen ornaments from his neck and leading him to the city square amidst the beating of lashes with whips (*kasalayachiva*), sprinkling dust, ashes and filth on his body, then putting him in prison tying his feet to a wooden frame (*haḍibandhana*). He was deprived of food, drink and beaten with lashes thrice a day leading to his death finally.

The Jain text ‘*Ācārāṅga Cūrṇī*’³⁷ mentions about a priest who robbed a purse of a merchant containing wealth. Such robberies were termed as ‘*Ganthibhedhaka*’ in Jain literature.

Jain text ‘*Paṇhavāgarāṇa ṭikā*’³⁸ mentions 7 types of robbers and 18 ways of encouraging theft. The ‘*Praśnavyākaraṇa Sūtra*’³⁹ in the third chapter titled ‘*Udattādāna*’ elaborately deals on stealing in the form of conversation by Sudharmasvāmī to Jambusvāmī. Stealing is defined as worshipping a thing that belongs to someone other than the self without the owner’s permission or his knowledge. It mentions four types of stealing namely ‘Stealing things of owners’ [*Svāmi Adatta*], ‘Stealing life or limbs (taking away life)’ [*Jīva*], stealing from teachers [*Guru*] and stealing from *Tīrthāṅkara*. These can also be based on the thing stolen (*Dravya*),

place (*Kṣetra*), time (*Kāla*) and the intent or cause for stealing [*Bhāva*]. The text elaborately also gives description of thieves stating that they reside in hilly areas, move about in odd hours in cremation grounds, forests, ruins, stone huts and undulating areas. Sometimes they lived on flesh of wild animals and roots or had to consume half-burnt corpses. They wore turbans of black, red, green, yellow or white colors. The '*Praśnavyākaraṇa Sūtra*' also mentions 30 synonyms of words meaning 'stealing' or 'theft'. The text also mentions about sea robbers (pirates) who waved black and white flags at other ships and robbed sea travelers.

The Jain text '*Kāma Kumbhādikathāsaṅgraha*'⁴⁰ mentions about a prince named Baṅkacūḍa who turned as the chief of thieves, taught new methods of stealing to several bandits and was transformed by an ascetic who mentioned four vows to him leading him to a noble life later.

The Jain '*Pārśvanāthacarita*'⁴¹ (PNC) mentions about seven kinds of thieves. It also mentions about how thieves enter a king's palace by means of unknown magic spells called *Kṛṣṇākṣara* as well as some lock breaking charms. PNC [I.570ff] narrates the story about a person Skandila well versed in magical charms and teaches a thief being pursued by the king's guards for having stolen a jewel casket. The thief acquires '*Adhiṣṭhāyinividyā*' and obtains a celestial car, poses himself as a *Vidhyādhara* holding on top of the rope near a tree and threatens the guards by holding a big stone stating that he would throw it down on whosoever injured his teacher Skandila. The soldiers inform the king who comes and learns how Skandila became his teacher. PNC [2.619ff] describes the story of a thief Mahābala who comes from a good family, loses his relatives and leads a dissolute life as a gambler and becomes a thief. He was accused by the king's guards when another thief who was pursued for theft of a jewel casket dropped it in front of him. They beat him with staffs and lead him to execution. PNC [6.447ff] mentions a merchant's son Vasanta who was spoilt in bringing up committing certain acts that make his father to drive him away from home. He becomes a vagabond beggar, sleeps in temples and becomes addicted to vices leading to committing theft. PNC [7.148ff] has a prince making signal to four thieves (known as *Caurasaṅjñā*) gaining their confidence, tricking them out of their valuable loot. PNC [8.124ff] describes the story of thief Bandhudatta who tries to rescue his wife Priyadarśana captive with a *Bhilla* chieftain named Caṇḍasena. Both Bandhudatta and his uncle Dhanadatta who are put in prison for stealing a jewel casket marked with king's name are cleared of suspicion after confession and freed. PNC [2.46ff] describes that theft is worse than murder. PNC [8.236ff] describes the story of Śrīgupta, son of a wealthy merchant who was honored by the king but goes down as a thief due to evil association. PNC [2.439ff] gives a story of a mother Candrā and her son Sarga who then curse each other and are reborn as daughter and son of two merchants. Innocently both get implicated in an act of a thief and are impaled on a stake. PNC [6.458ff] mentions a thief who enters a king's palace by means of a magical spell called *Kṛṣṇākṣara*. PNC [8.157ff] mentions a thief using a lock-breaking charm.

Jain texts also narrate story of thief Rauhiṇeya who during the reign of king Śreṇik led a gang of bandits. The '*Rauhiṇeya Carita*'⁴² (RC) of Devamūrti (undated) mentions about the conversion of a thief named Rauhiṇeya who hails from a family tradition of thieves. After his father died he is urged by his widowed mother to take up the profession. She arranges *Nyuñcanas* (some arrangement of decorations probably), lamp with seven wicks and applies the caste mark on his forehead giving her blessings as stated in RC [122] –

*nyuñcānāni vidhāyāsu pradīpariṃ saptavartibhiḥ | vidhāya tilakam mātā putrāyetyāśisam
dadau ||*

Rauhiṇeya was the son of Lohakhura and Rohiṇī. Lohakhura was in turn the son of Rūpyakhura and Rupyakhurā thus indicating a family tradition of thieves. Rauhiṇeya lived in one of the several families of thieves that dwelt in the caves of the *Vāibhāragiri* mountain range in *Rājagīha* (known as *Rājagṛha*) on the bank of the Ganges. The text states that the mountain had several trees, waterfalls and was infested with wild animals making sounds such as roars of lions and tigers, howling of jackals and hooting of owls. Several ascetics dwelt and meditated around the range living on bulbs, roots and fruits. One day as Rauhiṇeya came near city of *Rājagṛha*, his ears fell on the sermon of Lord Mahāvīra against the promise given to his dead father that he would not hear it. He was caught in an act of theft but could not be arrested without proof. King Śreṇik ordered his wise minister Abhayakumāra who tricked Rauhiṇeya into being dressed as a God living in a seven storey palace attended by beautiful maids posing as Goddesses. Rauhiṇeya sees through the trick played by Abhayakumāra remembering Lord Mahāvīra's sermon and transforms himself into a good citizen after being pardoned by the king. The Rauhiṇeya episode occurs in other Jain works as well such as the '*Mahāvīracaritra*'⁴³ of Hemacandra, the commentary of Hemacandra to the '*Yogaśāstra*', the '*Paryuṣaṇāṣṭāhnikavyākhyāna*' (15th CE), '*Upadeśaprāsāda*', various '*Abhayakumāracaritras*' and also in the drama '*Prabuddharauhiṇeya*'⁴⁴ that was edited later. Some other aspects of the story of Rauhiṇeya have been dealt by scholars in literature⁴⁵. An interesting aspect of the story is the means by which thieves were detected and arrested. Abhayakumāra detected Rauhiṇeya in a Jain temple when the latter came in the guise of a Jain disciple. He did not make the necessary rituals around the assembly as required by Jain principles and concluded that he must be a thief. While tricking him into his plan, Abhayakumāra also noticed that Rauhiṇeya made obeisance to him in a worldly language not used by the Jainas. He was then arrested but Abhayakumāra turned down all his proposals to face any ordeal to prove his innocence. Abhayakumāra then brought an automated contrivance in the form of a beautiful lady (called thief catcher) to strike a blow with the sword when thieves bent in front of it. Rauhiṇeya refused and was tricked by the minister when he worshipped the puppet with ablutions of a strong mixture of water and liquor that he offered to Rauhiṇeya to drink. Rauhiṇeya became unconscious when struck by the blow after being intoxicated by the drink. He was later moved into the seven storey palace. The text RC [17] has king Śreṇik entering into a pact with thief Lohakhura to furnish him provisions on the condition that he stop pillaging the king's city of *Rājagṛha*. The '*Samyaktvaakumudī*'⁴⁶ (SK) mentions king Uditodaya and his minister Subuddhi who make themselves invisible, wander through the city at night and detect thief Suvarṇakhura (or Lohakhura). Lohakhura was skilled in the use of magic pills and salves for invisibility. All the three listen to a merchant's account of his conversion to Jainism. Lohakhura makes himself invisible and then ate with the king habitually. He was tricked to shed tears so that the collyrium (*Añjana*) was washed away from his eyes and thus made visible to all. Lohakhura was then caught and impaled.

The '*Samarādityasarikṣepa*'⁴⁷ [SS] of Pradyumnācārya has a teacher Skandarudra who presents his pupil Caṇḍarudra with a magic pill that makes him invisible as stated in the text SS [6.114]. Likewise the text SS [4.128ff] also presents a story where a teacher presents a pupil a charm for breaking locks on the condition that he does not utter a lie. The pupil

transgresses, steals goods after uttering a lie and is caught finally being punished. SS [6.455ff] describes a story of Dharaṇa and his wife Lakṣmī who plots the destruction of an enemy by depositing the loot. The motif of depositing loot to destroy an enemy is also found in the story of Cakradeva, a merchant and Yajñadeva (son of a *Purohita*) in SS [2.187ff]. The text SS [6.93ff] has Lakṣmī abandoning her husband Dharaṇa for a thief or robber Caṇḍarudra who applies a magic pill (*guṭikā*) given by his preceptor Skandarudra. He deposits all loot with Dharaṇa and implicates him in a case. In SS [4.104ff], a merchant Dhana has been cast into the ocean by his wife who plots his death. He saves himself by a wooden plank swimming to the shore, finally arriving at Śrāvasti where the treasure of king Vicāradhavala has been robbed. Dhana is falsely implicated in a case due to possession of a necklace and ordered to be executed. He resuscitates the prince bitten by a snake using a charm given by a gambler and is finally freed by the king. In SS [5.30ff] prince Sanatkumāra secures release of highly trained thieves. The king orders thieves to be executed without the prince's knowledge. SS [6.73ff] has Dharaṇa rescuing *Cāṇḍāla* Maurika who is unjustly accused of theft by ransoming him of a huge sum.

Hemavijaya's '*Kathāratnākara*'⁴⁸ (KR) also has some interesting narratives of thieves. The text KR [Story No. 82] mentions about a thief who steals fruits from a mango tree in a pleasure garden of queen Cellaṇā and king Śreṇik by magically bending it towards him by a spell in order to satisfy the desires of his pregnant wife. The minister Abhayakumāra tricks the thief by narrating a story of a lady who steals flowers from a garden and is desired in the process by four people - her husband, the gardener, some robbers and a demon. The real thief responds to a question put by Abhayakumāra and finally he is delivered to the king. KR [Story No. 129] has another novel method by a thief Vasana who steals the golden peacock placed by the king Puruṣadatta on top of a Śiva temple carefully not disturbing the sleeping guards. He tricks them by carrying the loot along with a dead child fooling the guards that follow him by making false cries. Along with assistance of another thief Chatura, Vasana buries the loot in a cemetery with the dead child and enacts as though removing it himself, giving the stolen artefact to courtesan Rūpasenā to prove his ingenuity. In the process, he sticks the dagger into several other dead bodies as well as into hand of Chatura who keeps quiet. Later Vasana cleverly implicates Chatura in the case and tells the king that one who is suffering from dagger wounds cannot be cured without betel leaf (*Tāmbūla*) which increases its market value. Vasana adores the garb of an ascetic and as he sells it himself in the market, one of the slave girls of Rūpasenā comes to buy the exorbitant betel leaves and thus he implicates Chatura stating that he is living with her and gets him arrested. The king on learning the matter after investigation was pleased with the cleverness of both thieves thus appointing both of them as chamberlains in the royal court. KR [Story No. 45] mentions about a magic ring that protects against thieves. The text KR [Story No. 61] has thief Musala paying a friendly visit to thief Siddhisuta and notices a golden bowl which he decides to steal. The latter aware of it hangs the bowl full of water above his head near the bed but Musala sucks it out using a reed when Siddhisuta is fast asleep. He then hides the bowl in a pond. Siddhisuta feels Musala's wet feet and shoes, tracks his footsteps to the pond and then takes it out. At the breakfast next day, Siddhisuta chides Musala (when he has a doubt) that it was the same bowl which he had thrown in the pond. KR [Story No. 110] narrates the episode of a thief Kharpara who uses the oil in lamp hung before the statue of Goddess Harasiddhi to lubricate the cakes he bakes on coals of a funeral pyre. She sticks out her tongue to frighten but he asks Her to draw it back else he would smash the statue into pieces with stone.

In this act, he obtains a reward in gold as well as magical powers from the Goddess as She had been threatened by him. KR [Story No. 178] has king Vikrama who catches four thieves with magic powers but releases them after verifying their skill and truthfulness.

The ‘*Vardhamāna Deśānā*’⁴⁹ of Śrī Śubhavadhanagaṇi dated to about 1495 CE is inspired by the seventh *Aṅga* of *Śvetāmbara* Jains named ‘*Ubāśagdasao*’ (also known as ‘*Upāsakadaśa*’). It describes the story of a thief Sahasramalla who lived with his aged mother. He disguised himself pretty well and tricked various merchants and a dancing girl stealing their jewels, clothes, horses finally even tricking the chief of Police and king himself by posing as an expert in massaging his limbs. Finally, Sahasramalla realizes that he has no one else to steal and on hearing the sermon of a monk Vasuddha transforms into a noble citizen being pardoned by the king. That thieves were well versed in ‘*Ākāśagāminīvidyā*’ (the art of flying) is also evident from the story of Kesarī, a thief who wore a pair of magic sandals that enabled him to fly and loot the citizens. The text ‘*Vardhamāna Deśānā*’ states that Kesarī used to offer gems at feet of temple deity and was finally found by the king himself later surrendering himself to a monk.

The ‘*Śrādhanākathāprabandha*’⁵⁰ (or *Kathākośa*) of Prabhācandra (11th CE) has a story of a thief named Sūrya in the *Upagūhanākhyānaka*. He disguised as a novice (*kṣullaka*) on the orders of Suvīra, son of king Yaśodhvaja and queen Suśīma who lived in Pāṭalīputra. He had the passion of possessing the priceless cat’s eye gem crowned on the umbrella of a highly protected idol of Lord Pārśvanātha that was with the merchant Jinendrabhakta. Sūrya went to *Tāmralipta* and inspired the people of villages and towns and this reached the ears of merchant Jinendrabhakta. He set out for a voyage after assigning Sūrya to guard the jewel after being impressed by him. Sūrya stole the jewel at midnight but was caught due to the lustre of the gem. He pleaded at the merchant who just returned but to conceal the fault regarding the religion Jinendrabhakta pardoned the thief.

This tale of thief Sūrya is also narrated in the ‘*Yaśastilakacampū*’⁵¹ (YC) of Somadeva (10th c. A.D.). The YC [Book V] narrates the story of a thief who was produced in the court of king Sudatta having being accused of murder and robbing the wealth of a barber while he was asleep. The thief is condemned by the judges to imprisonment and torture so that he might expire in 10 to 12 days. Somadeva states in the text YC [Book III] that a thief on account of his wickedness suspects another even though he is not a thief. The text also narrates episode of another thief Lalita, the misguided son of a king who turned as thief. He stole the necklace of the queen of Kuśāgrapura. However he was followed by the city police and threw away the necklace to evade them. In course of this process, he acquires the magical powers that Dharasena was attempting to achieve by certain rites. Later the thief became a Jaina ascetic and attained salvation. Elsewhere the episode of prince Vāriṣena (the son of king Śreṇik of Magadha) who was implicated on theft of a necklace of a merchant’s wife is narrated. The necklace was stolen actually by a thief Mrgavega at the instance of his mistress, a courtesan named Magadhasundarī. The thief then put the necklace in front of Vāriṣena to evade the police.

The ‘*Kuvalayāmālā*’⁵² of Udyotanasūrī narrates the story of a merchant Sthānu who was pushed into a well by Māyāditya, another treacherous merchant from Vāranasī. A party of robbers saved Sthānu from the well and gave him his share of five jewels. The ‘*Upadeśamālā*’⁵³ (dated to 12th CE) of Hemacandra Mālādhārin describes a horde of thieves (*dhātī*) well practiced in *ṭhagavidyā* (trickster’s wisdom and magic spells to break locks on houses) who were

put to flight by Samayarāja. The text also mentions that the sons of king Adṛṣṭasaṁcaya and Aśubhaparīṇati were deluded by certain *Vidyās* using which they could open locks and gain access to houses.

The five vows on non-stealing to be observed by all *Śrāvakas* and monastics as stated in Pūjyapādācārya's '*Sarvārthasiddhi*'⁵⁴ [VII.27] was to not prompt the stealing of items either by oneself or through others or approval of theft, not receiving stolen goods, not to buy precious things cheaply in disordered state, not cheating others by use of false weights and measures as well as deceiving others with artificial gold or gems. In the context of the *Jīvaśarīravāda* (body-soul relation discussions) between king Pradeśī and Keśikumār Śramaṇ there are some views regarding theft expressed in the '*Rāyapaseṇiyasūtra*'⁵⁵ (Part II). King Pradeśī narrates some experiences with regard to punishment to various thieves such as one of them being placed in a narrow necked long iron pot with the iron cover being sealed air-tight. King Pradeśī questions that in spite of trusted men guarding it, the soul had escaped from the thief's body when he died even though there was no hole in the pot. Similarly when a thief who weighed same when alive as well as when he was dead indicated that the soul and body were different entities. Likewise another thief's corpse that was cut into number of pieces does not show anything other than flesh.

Many Jain texts allude to certain *Vidyās* or spells that a thief needed to be aware of so that he could steal. Such magical spells are mentioned in literature⁵⁶. Another text of Karnataka namely the '*Vaḍḍārādhanē*'⁵⁷ in Kannada language attributed to Śivakoṭi Ācārya dated to about 10th c. A. D. has interesting details on *Choraśāstra*. It states that the crown prince Yamadaṇḍa studied '*Surakha*' [a treatise on science of catching a thief that is not available now]. Likewise, the prince made his friend, the city guard's son Vidyutchora, bet on the act of thieving and how he would find him out. Vidyutchora is supposed to have also studied '*Karapaṭaśāstra*' [treatise on thievery] which is attributed to Kharpara as stated in the *Kathāsaritasāgara* accordingly -

*tanage takka kaḷḷaranārayva teranampelvi surakhamembodan kaltonānuṁ kaḷvu pāyamam pelvi
karapaṭa śāstramam kaltenimtemaganyonyā prītiyindan kālamsale||*

The text also lists the aids and tools used by Vidyutchora that he manifests these arts throughout the story. These are as follows-

*vidyuccoranembom kaḷḷanātaṁ jṛmbhinī stambhini mohini sarṣapī tālodghāṭini vidyā
mantracūrṇa yogaghuṭikāñjanameṁdivumodalādagodeya
taskaraśāstramgaḷolādamānukuśalanantappa kaḷḷam polila kasavarimgaḷanirulkaḷdu*

These include charms to cause the inmates of a house to sleep or yawn (*jṛimbhinī*), stupefy the movements of inmates (*Stambhana*), hypnotize them (*Mohinī*), reducing one's size to a mustard seed (*Sarṣapī*) spells for opening locks (*Tālodghāṭanī Vidyā*), magic powder for invisibility (*Mantracūrṇa*), Magic pills, collyrium to be applied on eyes as well as ointments. (*Yogaghuṭikā* and *Añjana siddhi*). These were known to thieves and were part of their knowledge or skills in these arts.

The '*Sūyadaṅga*'⁵⁸ (also known as '*Sūtrakṛtāṅga*') quotes the arts of '*Jṛimbhinī*' and '*Thambhinī*'. The text [2.2.15] also mentions *Osvaṇim* (art of casting people to sleep known as *Avasvāpinividya*). The '*Ambaḍacaritra*'⁵⁹ of Amarasūrī mentions a great magician who could

fly in air, change humans to animals and vice versa as stated in literature. The Jain texts also supply rich information on art of stealing. Some texts state that *Sakka* put to magic sleep the mother of *Tīrthaṅkara* Ṛṣabha. Each verse of *Bhaktāmara* stotra of Māṇatuṅga was claimed to break open locked doors⁶⁰. King Harisena received from monk Viśvabhūti the secret of preparing collyrium to render one invisible. Sanatkumāra had a magic shawl that rendered the wearer to become invisible. The ‘*Parīśiṣṭaparvan*’⁶¹(PP) (known also as ‘*Sthavirāvalīcaritra*’) by Hemachandra (12th CE) refers to *Ākāśagāminīvidyā* (the art of flying). The text also has some interesting narratives of thieves. Robber Cilāya opened the eastern gates of the city of *Rājaḡṛha* by reciting lock breaking charms. The PP [2.173ff] narrates the story of Jambukumāra, son of a rich merchant Ṛṣabhadatta and his wife Dharaṇīdevī. A thief named Prabhava along with other bandits loot the house of the merchant on the eve of the marriage of Jambukumāra to the daughters of eight wealthy merchants. Jambukumāra’s spell stupefies the 500 men of Prabhava who was a prince by birth (son of Vindhyaṛāja, king of Jaipur) but a thief by profession. Prabhava knew the art of breaking open locks by spells (*Tāluggḥādanīvijā*) and asked Jambukumāra to teach him the art of stupefying people. However by being influenced by Ārya Sudharmasvāmī’s wisdom, Prabhava along with his 500 men (after being pardoned by king Kuṇika of Magadha), Jambukumāra and his eight wives and their parents all got initiated and transformed into monks.

Rauhiṇeya knew several magic herbs, amulets and charms thus saving himself when attacked by several people. He could not be bitten by snakes, burnt of fire, bound by thongs, affected by poison and could make an attacking party turn upon each other. Rūpyakhura could stop and point blade of a sword to an opponent striking a blow at him that made him glued to the spot. The ‘*Samarāiccakāhā*’⁶² (SMK) of Haribhadrasūrī (459-529 CE) is a collection of stories. One story mentions Nārāyaṇa receiving two charms from his teacher that enabled him to fly in air and another to open locks. The SMK mentions that experts of *Dharmaśāstras* were summoned by a king to deliver appropriate penalty to a thief. The text also states that the hands, feet, ears and nose of a man who stole another’s property was to be cut off in public spaces and he was put to death. The text also mentions that a thief Chaṇḍarudra had a magic spell named ‘*Paradiṭṭi Mohaṇī*’ which would make one invisible. It was his preceptor Skandarudra who presented Chaṇḍarudra with the magic pill to make himself invisible when it was applied to his eyes. The thief Vijaya is said to have taught various spells to his pupil Cilāya. Such charms are elaborated in the text of ‘*ṣaṇmukḥakalpa*’ and some of them are mentioned in early poetical literature and dramas as discussed previously.

The Jain text ‘*Vāsudevahinḍī*’⁶³ (VH) of Sanghadāsa Gaṇi and Dharmadāsa Gaṇi, a Jaina version of Sanskrit ‘*Bṛhatkathā*’ of Guṇāḍhya gives some interesting features of thieves. It mentions the story of Agaḍadatta, disciple of Drḍhaprahārī who was successful in catching a thief dressed up as a mendicant holding a trident. The thief was well versed in breaking houses with implements from the backyard, sprinkles sleeping powder on thugs, pulls out a sword from tridents and stores his stolen goods in a underground passage at the end of a crematorium. Agaḍadatta kills the thief who plots his murder while dying and gives his sword asking him to meet his sister who lives at the corner of the crematorium. He asked him to marry her and enjoy the riches of the stolen wealth. Agaḍadatta escapes from the ploy of the thief’s sister to kill him by rolling over a huge stone on his sleeping couch. He then leads her to the king who then confiscates all the stolen wealth. Agaḍadatta then marries Śyāmā, daughter of Drḍhaprahārī’s

neighbour and as he was on the way to Ujjain, the party rested under a tree in the jungle. Some versions of the story state that he married the king's daughter Kamalāsena. Dhanapūjak, another thief who had come to avenge the killing of his friend also met with the same fate and was killed. The commentator Devendra to the text mentions some interesting features of thieves in the tale of Aḡaḡadatta. Thieves are said to frequent the houses of courtesans, gambling houses, stalls of bakers, sheds in parks, huts of ascetics, empty temples, markets and forests. Interestingly the thief who was on the verge of death after being wounded by Aḡaḡadatta asks him to cremate his body with full honours.

The story of thief Lohakhura is elaborated in texts like '*Malayasundarikathoddhāra*'⁶⁴ of Dharmachakra (14th CE), '*Mahābala Malayasundarī Rāsa*', '*Malayasundarīcaritra*'⁶⁵ of Kesarasurī and '*Mahābala Malayasundarikathā*' of Māṇikyasundara (15th CE). Lohakhura kidnaps Malayasundarī, the daughter of king Vīradhavalā and queen Champakamālā who was married to prince Mahābala. The prince fought the thieves and killed Lohakhura. The '*Mallināthacarita*'⁶⁶ refers to a village (*Hallisaka*) turbulent with dances of robber's women. The text [7.804] also refers to a lotus shaped breach. The '*Upamitibhāvaprapañcakathā*'⁶⁷ of Siddharṣi Gaṇi (10th CE) describes the barbarous treatment given to robber Abhaggasena before being executed. He was caught and brought before the streets, his offences were proclaimed and he was made to sit in the square. His eight uncles were beaten with thongs and killed before him and he was made to eat their own flesh and drink their blood. Thefts of an ordinary nature or most daring kind were punished capitally.

Police officers besmeared the bodies of criminals with soot, green grass, red earth and ashes, crowning their heads with a garland of shoes, parasol made of old articles was held over them, then mounting them on an ugly white ass, taken in procession amidst the beating of drums, and led in a southerly direction to the execution ground.

Several ancient texts punish the guilty thieves by various ordeals such as by fire, sacred water, a weighing balance, poison or rice. Rauhiṇeya was a master of charms and spells and not allowed to undergo ordeals. He wanted to clear himself from the charges of theft by dragging out a snake from a jar (an ordeal in those times) and also by ordeals of fire, sacred water and poison. Abhayakumāra, the minister administered the *Kośa* ordeal to Rauhiṇeya with some modifications. The *Kośa* ordeal involved the process of putting the idols of some deities into water. Some general rituals were performed to the idols and people used to wait for some weeks. If during that time no mis-happening occurred in the life of the accused or any of his relatives he was declared innocent. Several other procedures of punishment levied to thieves are discussed in literature.

The '*Prabandhacintāmaṇi*'⁶⁸ of Merutuṅga (14th CE) describes the story of Vanarāja who is destined to be a king but becomes a thief temporarily. He digs a tunnel into a merchant's house to steal but ends up putting his hands into a bowl of curds. He then gives up the act of stealing stating as to how he could steal from the house where he had eaten food.

The '*Kathākośa*'⁶⁹ of unknown origin (unlike other texts of similar titles) being a collection of stories mentions about Mitrānanda who dies innocently as a thief because of a fault in a previous birth. Another story in the same text mentions about a thief adorned for execution who falls at the feet of prince Vīrāṅgada to protect him. The prince does so at the price of being banished by his father.

A Jain tale⁷⁰ (found in '*Kathākośa*' of Prabhachandra) also narrates the story of a thief Garaka who was infatuated by the beauty of Vīravatī, the wife of merchant Dutta, the son of

Dhanamitra. He used to visit her often when Dutta was away on a voyage to Ratnadvīpa. While Dutta was returning through a jungle, another thief Sahasrabhaṭṭa follows him and keeps a watch on him. Meanwhile Garaka is caught and hanged on a pole in the outskirts of the city. Unable to disclose the secret love to her husband, Vīravatī steps out of her house with a sword in hand to meet Garaka. She finally ends up wounding Sahasrabhaṭṭa who has been following her but he keeps silent. She then steps over dead bodies and kisses her dying lover and returns back to her house. With blood on her lips she falsely implicates Dutta in a case of cutting her lips and he is also ordered by the king to be hanged. Sahasrabhaṭṭa who has watched the entire happenings intervenes to the court in disguise and narrates the episode to the king. Finally Vīravatī is sentenced to be hanged after she is dragged in the city with her hair cut by the guards.

Jinasena Desavratī's '*Vardhamānapurāṇa*'⁷¹ [Chap. XV] mentions about Vidyutprabha, son of Vidyunnāma and Guṇavati who leaves the land and joins 500 robbers becoming their chief. He is named as Vidyutchora and was well versed in the art of stealing. The '*Tilakamañjarī*'⁷² of Dhanapāla refers to the exclusion of dragging of feet in case of those who committed theft and took to their heels. The '*Triṣaṣṭhiśalākāpuruṣacarita*'⁷³ (TSSPC) is an elaborate narration of lives of 63 great persons in the Jain canons. TSSPC [Chap. V] describes the story of a thief Kāka who was devoted to other men's wives looting several cities.

Several glimpses of theft in *Kāvya*s by other Jain poets have been dealt in literature^{74,75}. Thus we find of the art of Stealing in ancient Jain literature.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

Ancient Sanskrit and regional literature⁷⁶ has rich descriptions of art of stealing. Several aspects of theft in such texts are dealt by scholars such as Maurice Bloomfield and others^{77,78}. Similar descriptions are also found in Jain literature^{79,80}. Though it may seem that these descriptions are drawn from Sanskrit texts, there are other features that are specially found in Jain sources. The descriptions in some texts make us wonder as to whether '*Cauryakalā*' was to be considered as *Dharma* or *Adharma*. This is evident from discussions in texts like the '*Dharmacauryārasāyana*' of Gopālayogīndra. In Jain literature also several interesting aspects about theft are described and it might be worth mentioning some of them as below. There are descriptions of hideouts of thieves such as *Śālāṭavī* and those around cities like *Rājaḡṛha*. Several thieves adopt novel methods of stealing as elaborated in some texts. These are evident in the stories of Skandila, Vijaya, Musala, Kharpara, Vasana, Sahasramalla, Rauhiṇeya and Maṇḍiya. Most of the thieves were well versed in various arts and magical spells such as those possessed by Vidyutchora, Lohakhura, Kesari, Prabhava, Skandarudra, Harisena, Rūpyakhura, Nārāyaṇa, Cilāya, Caṇḍarudra, Sanatkumāra and Rauhiṇeya. It is also noted in these texts that several innocent people were falsely implicated in theft cases by other thieves. This is evident in the episodes of Mitrānanda, Vīrāṅgada, Dhana, Dharaṇa, Candrā, Sarga, Vāriṣena and Dutta. Several other people coming from good families go down as a thief due to evil association as seen in episodes of Mahābala, Śrīgupta, Vasanta and Lalita. One also notices instances of one thief depositing loot in another person's place or implicating another thief in the case as seen in the narratives of Vasana and Chatura and also Mṛgavega. Strangely some episodes of thieves catching hold of another thief and producing him before kings is also

noted in Jain literature as evident from episodes of Garaka and Sahasrabhaṭṭa. The association of women in acts of theft or with other thieves acts as a motif in stories of Lakṣmī, Vīravatī and Rūpasena. Various thieves also realized their mistakes, repented for them and transformed into noble citizens as seen in episodes of Sahasramalla, Prabhava, Kesari and Rauhiṇeya. Descriptions of different types of torture, punishments and judicial ordeals and trials are found in texts like ‘Vipākasūtra’, ‘Nāyādhammakahā’, ‘Yaśastilakacampū’, ‘Rauhiṇeyacharitra’, ‘Upamitibhāvaprapañcakathā’ and ‘Tilakamañjarī’. Strangely some episodes show that thieves were appointed as chamberlains based on their cleverness as in the story of Vasana. Thieves generally struck the houses of wealthy merchants or kings and also kidnapped women. Lohakhura, Prabhava and Vijaya were famous in such acts. The theft of idols or its artifacts is mentioned in the episode of thief Sūrya in *Kathākośa* of Prabhācandra. Stealing of temple articles is also evident in some texts as seen in episodes of Vasana stealing a peacock image atop a temple or Kharpara using the oil from a temple lamp. Interestingly, there are some scientific and technical marvels in these narratives such as those noted in episodes of Rauhiṇeya wherein mention is made of a seven storey building and a thief catching puppet that strikes blows. In story of Aḡaḡadatta we do find mention of huge rolling stones that were made to fall on a sleeping couch. Some thieves also give up their professions as in stories of Sahasramalla, Rauhiṇeya and Vanarāja. There are narratives involving various sections of society such as a gardener, barber, monks, traders, courtesans, kings and ascetics afflicted by thieves or also helping them. Studies in such episodes may throw interesting light on the customs, habits, economy, dress and ornaments and other aspects in Jain literature that will also help in dating some of the texts by suitable archaeological and inscriptional interdisciplinary studies of those periods. There needs to be documentation of various laws, codes of non-stealing or theft as well as philosophical discussions pertaining to thefts from various other Jain sources although some of them are found in some texts such as ‘*Praśnavyākaraṇa Sūtra*’, Pūjyapādācārya’s ‘*Sarvārthasiddhi*’ and ‘*Rāyapaseṇiya Sutra*’. Still several stories about theft and its related arts may be found in untapped Jain *Campūs*, *Kāvya*s and other Jain literary sources that are yet to be researched so as to bring out full details of *Choraśāstra* in ancient Jain texts. These need to be also supplemented by Folk beliefs, customs and Ballads on arts of stealing and brought to light by the scholarly world. This paper is just a humble attempt in that direction as it reveals the art of theft as evident from Jain literature.

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